

Quantum Mechanical Basis Functions and the Hamiltonian

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The notion of basis functions, and decompositions of functions in terms of bases, seems to come from linear algebra. In other words, it is mathematical. Quantum mechanical wavefunctions, however, are associated with such a mathematical structure because for a given Hamiltonian, bound states form a complete basis. As a result, one may mathematically write a wavefunction in terms of a basis set and consider overlaps $\langle W_1 | W_2 \rangle$, which are taken to represent physical transitional information. In this note, we, however, examine whether such basis overlaps make physical sense in all cases.

We consider the association of basis functions with the Hamiltonian in the problem. In particular, we focus on the case of a shifted ground state oscillator wavefunction. Even though mathematically, this may be written as a linear superposition of wavefunctions centered at $x=0$, i.e. not shifted, the shifted ground state and the basis functions about $x_0=0$ are associated with different Hamiltonians. Thus, we question whether one should consider such overlaps. This seems to be related to using a basis set corresponding to one physical Hamiltonian (with a certain potential) and mathematically applying it to a system with a different Hamiltonian. Mathematically, this is possible, but physically it does not seem to make sense. The shifted oscillator ground state gives the sense that one has the same Hamiltonian, but it seems that the potential is shifted and so one should not associate it with a linear superposition of wavefunctions based about $x=0$. We further use the idea of the correspondence principle to try to strengthen this argument.

Basis Functions

Basis functions are a standard of linear algebra, allowing one to write one function of a variable x in terms of a weighted sum of basis functions of the same variable x . This appears to be a mathematical process which is associated with quantum mechanics to a certain degree. For example, a given Hamiltonian has a set of bound states which form a basis. One may write a general wavefunction as a superposition of such a set of basis functions and expect it to have meaning, i.e. for there to be an overlap of this wavefunction with a given energy eigenstate. The question we ask is: Are there limitations to this approach of writing a wavefunction in terms of various basis states? We argue that there are.

Quantum Mechanics and the Hamiltonian

A quantum bound system is governed by a certain Hamiltonian. In a simple nonrelativistic case, :

$$H = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + V(x) \quad ((1))$$

$V(x)$ is taken from classical physics and represents a physical entity, usually associated with force. As a result, one does not have a purely mathematical situation and we argue this has to be taken into account in certain cases.

An obvious situation is that of a basis set corresponding to $V_1(x)$ applied to a system with a different potential $V_2(x)$. Even though this is possible mathematically, it does not seem to have much physical meaning, unless perhaps $V_1(x)$ and $V_2(x)$ are very similar. For example, $V_2(x)$ may equal $V_1(x)$ plus a perturbation term. In such case, one may solve the problem using a Hamiltonian with $V_1(x)$ and consider a linear superposition of some eigenstates of this problem to try to approximate a solution of H with $V_2(x)$. If $V_1(x)$ and $V_2(x)$, however, are completely different, one

has very different physical situations and it is not clear why a basis set from one should be associated with a solution with a completely different potential.

Shifted Wavefunctions

Using basis functions from one Hamiltonian to describe a solution for a different Hamiltonian is usually not done. In the case of a shifted wavefunction, however, one may be tempted to think that the same Hamiltonian applies. For example, if one considers a shifted ground state wavefunction:

$$W(x, x_0) = C \exp(-a(x-x_0)(x-x_0)) \quad ((2))$$

this wavefunction is associated with a ground state energy $E_0 = .5 \hbar \omega$, where $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$.

$W(x, x_0)$ may be mathematically expressed in terms of basis functions of a non-shifted oscillator, i.e.

$$W(x, x_0) = \sum_n c_n W_n(x) \quad ((3))$$

One may make the association ((3)) thinking the oscillator Hamiltonian applies in both cases. Actually, however, it seems two different Hamiltonians exist, namely;

$$H_1 = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + .5k(x-x_0)(x-x_0) \quad ((4a)) \text{ and}$$

$$H_2 = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + .5k(x)(x) \quad ((4b))$$

We argue that ((4a)) and ((4b)) are different even though the potentials have a similar mathematical structure. As in the case of the previous paragraph, we would caution against an expansion ((3)) as functions of different Hamiltonians are used. The shifted ground state is still an oscillator ground state and seems to have nothing to do with excited oscillator states.

Basis State Orthogonality

For the quantum oscillator, adjacent energy level n states are orthogonal due to even-odd spatial behaviour of energy eigenstates. For example, the ground state is odd, the first excited state, even, etc. This ensures successive states are orthogonal, in fact all are. A shifted eigenstate (i.e. shifted in x) breaks this even-odd property when compared with states about $x_0=0$, but it has its own new set of even-odd eigenfunctions associated with the shifted potential. Thus, as argued above one should not mix states from different Hamiltonians unless the Hamiltonians are very close. We argue that a state shifted in x by quite some distance does not have a Hamiltonian which is similar.

Correspondence Principle

We try to link the above arguments to the correspondence principle which states that in the high energy level limit, a quantum bound state becomes close to the classical one. If one tries to expand a shifted wavefunction in terms of solutions of the non-shifted case, we argue that one should see if such an association holds in the high n limit. In the high n limit, i.e. a classical limit, one would not compare a solution centered at one x_0 with one associated with $x=0$ some distance away. In such a case, we argue that one should be careful when using basis functions in quantum mechanics and trying to obtain overlap information for overlaps which may not have physical relevance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though quantum mechanics is associated with a set of basis functions linked with a Hamiltonian, and perhaps other operators which commute with this Hamiltonian, this is a unique basis set which applies to a particular problem. If one has two Hamiltonians which are very similar, i.e. one is a perturbation of the other, one might consider solving the simpler Hamiltonian case, as in the deuteron problem, and using linear superposition of basis eigenfunctions to try to describe a solution of the perturbed Hamiltonian. If the two Hamiltonians, however, are different, we argue that there is no physical reason to try to use a basis set from one to describe a solution of the different Hamiltonian.

A somewhat subtle example of this seems to be linked with shift in x a solution of an oscillator. In such a case, one may think that the shifted oscillator solution is associated with the same Hamiltonian as that of an oscillator centered at $x_0=0$. The potentials in both cases, however, are different, namely $.5k(x-x_0)(x-x_0)$ and $.5kxx$. As a result, one may mathematically write the ground state shifted wavefunction in terms of a set of oscillator solutions about $x_0=0$, but if x_0 and 0 are not close, it seems there is no reason to associate the two, even if both are oscillator type solutions. We further argue that the correspondence principle supports this argument. Thus, we caution against simply using mathematical basis function expansions and considering overlaps as representing physical transitional information.